

Analysis Cinderella Complex In Eiffel I'm In Love Dan Fairish by Tania Intan

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Abstract

Cinderella complex is a psychological tendency (in women), which consistently experiences dependence and always hopes for protection (from men). This research aims to reveal the Cinderella complex internalized in female characters in two teens lit Indonesia entitled Eiffel I'm in Love by Rahmania Arunita and Fairish by Esti Kinasih. Cinderella shapes The complex that is revealed in the two youth novels is that the female character depends on the male character and maintains a spoiled and weak nature which is attributed to a feminine character. As a result, there is no independence and the ability of female characters to solve problems.

Keywords: *cinderella complex, postfeminism, teen lit, feminist literary criticism*

INTRODUCTION

Besides chick-lit, teen lit or teenager literature (teen literature) was a new trend in Indonesian literature in the early 2000s, whose emergence brought a breath of fresh air through themes and storytelling styles that characterize popular literature. Popular literature is indeed devoted or following the tastes of readers who can experience changes from time to time. The characteristics of popular literature include widely published, widely read, quickly sold in its time, and written to be traded with a ready-to-serve presentation.

Cinderella story is a traditional European fairy tale with around 700 versions that can be found in various parts of the world. In Indonesia story, The main story can be found in the story of Bawang Merah and Bawang Putih. Cinderella narrates the life of a beautiful and kind girl who lives with an evil stepmother and her two stepsisters. During their stay with them, Cinderella's character experienced various tortures. Her life just changed when a handsome prince found her glass slipper, married her, and they lived happily ever after.

METHOD

Analysis study this using a qualitative descriptive method that aims to describe a situation or phenomenon by using scientific procedures to answer the actual problem. The object of research that

became the data source was two students lit Indonesia entitled Eiffel I'm In Love (2014) and Fairish (2004), which were selected considering the novels' titles as best seller title titles.

Data collection techniques were carried out using reading, listening, and note-taking techniques with details of (a) determining the novel to be analyzed, (b) reading the novel repeatedly, and (c) classifying the data. The data analysis techniques in this study are (a) identifying the data that has been collected, (b) defining the data and then classifying it in detail so that it is easy to understand, (c) further analyzing the data, and (d) concluding.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Tita is a teenage girl who has an almost perfect life. He comes from a harmonious and well-established family, has a patient and understanding girlfriend, and his friends are always there for him, only Tita's mother is very protective. Teen lit Fairish tells the story of a young, sweet, and petite girl who attends one of the favorite high schools in Jakarta named Fairish. One day, a new student named Davi arrives, who is indifferent, tall, and very handsome.

When chick-lit considered adopting a postfeminist mindset because it always displays the character of a single female character, financially independent, modern in appearance and lifestyle, in several teens. lit it turns out that the application of the classical mindset is still found. Female characters like Tita still dream and make marriage their ultimate goal in life. This reality becomes ironic because issues that are counterproductive from a feminist perspective appear in *teen lit*, literature aimed at young millennial women

Dewi Candraningrum, a feminist activist, regrets that many girls today are hit by the cinderella complex. This could be influenced by the incessant broadcast of soap operas, Korean dramas, films, or novels with the theme of romance between poor girls and rich men. The influence of *this phenomenon* makes women laud men to marry them, fertilize them, and make them happy. Whereas the most important thing that should be understood by women is the awakening of awareness to enrich their horithemons, so that it is as women get space to live life to the fullest, according to their choice.

CONCLUSION

In the novel Eiffel, I'm in Love and Irish and Irish and IrisIriit has been proven that the Cinderella complex becomes an obstacle for female figures in forming independent, assertive, and initiative-taking characters. This syndrome is internalized in women's mentality since childhood, making them always depend on and expect help, especially from men. If only they want to free themselves from this dependence, women will stand firmly, move forward, and maximize all the potential that exists within themselves. Even though women are the subjects in the novel who tell the story from their point of view, their actual position in the story is the object being saved [male].

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